

In Situ Polymerization and Characterization of PA6/CFRTP Composites

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ABSTRACT

In this study, vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) was used for fabrication of thermoplastic composites. Generally, VaRTM is a low-cost manufacturing technique for thermoset resin composites; however, low viscosity monomer was used as resin to fabricate thermoplastic composites via VaRTM method in this study.

Polyamide 6 (PA6) is one of engineering plastics used for a wide range of applications, and its monomer called ϵ -caprolactam has very low viscosity even at a low temperature. During VaRTM process, ϵ -caprolactam can be polymerized to PA6 with catalyst and activator under a specific molding temperature. According to the experimental findings, at 140°C the monomer was polymerized very well and the resin impregnation was also satisfactory. Furthermore, bending strength and modulus and impact strength of the specimens at 140°C showed best values among those of other samples molded at other temperatures.

Another purpose of this study is to evaluate the polymerization kinetics of ϵ -caprolactam. However, polymerization and crystallization of ϵ -caprolactam occurs simultaneously, therefore it is difficult to investigate polymerization and crystallization kinetics, separately. In this study, the polymerization and crystallization processes with different heating rates were separated using Gaussian and Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in order to study the polymerization kinetics. Modeling results showed that the first order autocatalytic reaction model presents a very good fitting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites have been widely used in place of metallic materials, and one of the popular carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites is ϵ -caprolactam based CFRTP composites due to its watery viscosity and fast polymerization time. Researches on in situ polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam have already been carried out. Ahmadi et al. suggested that the correct ratio of monomer, catalyst and activator is a key component of the anionic ϵ -caprolactam polymerization, which leads to the least monomer residue and the best properties of PA6 samples [1-3]. In addition, various types of catalyst and activator had been used for anionic polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam to investigate polymerization rate, monomer conversion, mechanical properties, electrical conductivity, and so on [4-9]. Using these polymerization techniques, Gong et al. fabricated polyamide single polymer composites via resin transfer molding; however, the reaction time is too long for automotive industry [10, 11].

Numerous studies on polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam have been performed using various types and ratios of catalyst and activator. Only a few studies, however, have been conducted on ϵ -caprolactam based CFRTP composites using RTM process within several minutes in order to reduce the cycle time of molding processes.

In this study, we focused on the effect of molding temperature on the mechanical properties and polymerization kinetics. Meanwhile, heating rate plays an important role in polymerization and

crystallization kinetics, which can directly affect the mechanical properties of pure PA6 and CFRTCP composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

In this study, ϵ -caprolactam (DSM, Netherlands) was used as monomer, and it was mixed with catalyst and activator for anionic polymerization at specified molding temperatures. Sodium metal (DAEJUNG, Korea) and hexamethylene diisocyanate (HMDI) (Wako, Japan) were used as a catalyst and activator, respectively. In addition, plain carbon fabric (MUHAN COMPOSITES, Korea) was used as a reinforcement with thickness of 0.22mm, and the specification is shown as Table 1.

Figure 1: Anionic polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam

Table 1: Specification of carbon fabric

Product	Weaving Methods	Width (mm)	Wrap	Fill	Weight (g/m ²)
C-120	Plain	1000/1500	Carbon 3K	Carbon 3K	200

2.2 Process

Figure 2 shows the experimental setting of VaRTM process. Monomer and catalyst were melted in the oil bath, and 13 layers of carbon fabric were piled in the mold before molding.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the VaRTM process

The catalyst for the anionic polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam is sensitive for humidity in the air, so the container in the oil bath keep the vacuum condition during the melting process and the mold must be sealed well. Moreover, all the materials used in this study must be fully dried in order to prevent moisture from interfering with the polymerization process.

ϵ -Caprolactam was dried at 40 °C for 24 hours with silica gel blue in vacuum oven. Meanwhile, carbon fabric was washed with acetone to remove binding agent, which may decrease the interfacial performance between resin and fiber, before the installation into the lower mold, and it was also dried at 80 °C for 5 minutes to remove the moisture. A pre-specified ratio of ϵ -caprolactam and sodium metal

were melted at 110°C for 1 hour with vacuum condition. The dried carbon fabric was piled in the mold and sealed the mold well before injection.

After melting, activator was injected to the mixture of monomer and catalyst, and then transferred to the mold heated for 5 minutes for polymerization. The temperature of mold was set at 120°C, 140°C, 160°C, 180°C and 200°C, respectively. Finally, the specimen was released from the mold without cooling.

2.3 Characterization

In order to investigate mechanical properties of pure PA6 and CFRTP samples, the following tests were conducted.

First, content of unreacted monomer and content of water absorption, which may affect mechanical properties of products, were measured. Furthermore, three point bending tests (ASTM D790-10) and izod impact tests (ASTM D256) were carried out for the samples molded at different molding temperatures. Instron-5584 (Instron, UK) universal materials testing machine and Izod impact tester (SALT, Korea) were used to measure bending properties and impact properties of pure PA6 and CFRTP composites. Finally, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed (i.e. about 10mg each sample) in order to evaluate the crystallinity during the molding process,

3 MODELING ANALYSIS

Since polymerization and crystallization of ε-caprolactam occurs nearly simultaneously, so it is difficult to investigate polymerization and crystallization kinetics. Therefore, the exothermic peak can be separated by crystallization and polymerization peak. Polymerization peak follows Gaussian distribution (Eq. 1), whereas crystallization peak follows Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (Eq. 2).

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (1)$$

Where μ is mean or expectation of the distribution, σ is standard deviation and σ^2 is variance.

$$f(v) = f(v) \sqrt{\left(\frac{m}{2\pi kT}\right)^3} \times \pi v^2 e^{-\frac{mv^2}{2kT}} \quad (2)$$

Where m is the particle mass, k is the product of Boltzmann's constant and T is thermodynamic temperature.

There are many various modeling equations for polymerization kinetics. Among these models, Malkin's model is the most frequently used model, and the first order autocatalytic reaction model (Eq. 3) was used in this study for modeling of polymerization under non-isothermal condition. The reason why we use the first order autocatalytic reaction model is that we select the simplest formulas among the modeling equations which can fit the actual experimental data very well except chemical factors.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha) (1 + B_0 \alpha) \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 3, there are three parameters A_0 , E , B_0 , and the commercial program Matlab was used for curve fitting and the parameters.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

After polymerization, there still exists a certain amount of unreacted monomer, which is very hydroscopic and is readily dissolved in water. In order to check the conversion of ϵ -caprolactam, unreacted monomer and water absorption test was conducted.

The sample size is 60mm \times 10mm \times 3.75mm, and the results shown in Figure 3 are the average data of five samples in each case. Each sample was dried at 60 $^{\circ}$ C for 24 hours in a depressurized chamber, and its weight was measured and marked as W_0 . After that, each was put in hot water at 80 $^{\circ}$ C for 72 hours, and its weight was signed as W_2 . Finally, each sample was dried at 60 $^{\circ}$ C for 72 hours in a vacuum chamber again, and its weight recorded as W_1 . With these data, we can obtain the content of unreacted monomer and water absorption of PA6 and CFRTP composites using Eq. 3 and Eq. 4.

$$W_u = \frac{W_0 - W_1}{W_0} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$W_a = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_2} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

Where W_u is content of unreacted monomer and W_a is content of water absorption.

Figure 3 shows the percentage of the unreacted monomer (W_u) and the content of water absorption (W_a) of PA6 and CFRTP composites. It can be seen that the content of unreacted monomer and water absorption for both pure PA6 and CFRTP composites show lowest value at 140 $^{\circ}$ C.

Furthermore, both the contents of unreacted monomer and water absorption of pure PA6 and CFRTP have a similar tendency, which may indicate that the carbon fabrics which used as reinforcement rarely affect the polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam.

Figure 3: Content of unreacted monomer and water absorption of pure PA6 and CFRTP composites

Figure 4 represents the bending results of pure PA6 and CFRTP composites. It shows the highest value of the bending strength and bending modulus at 140 $^{\circ}$ C, at which the content of unreacted monomer and water absorption is the lowest. It seems to be correlated to the results above.

Figure 4: Bending strength and modulus of pure PA6 and CFRTP at different molding temperatures

It can be seen in Figure 5 that impact strength of pure PA6 molded at 120°C and 200°C is lower than that of other samples due to unreacted monomer. However, it shows that impact strength of the CFRTP composites, which were molded at 120°C and 200°C, shows much higher values than those of others. It may be that impregnation of carbon fibers at 120°C and 200°C is worse than that of others, and there is much unreacted monomer when it was molded at 120°C and 200°C. Specimens of CFRTP-120 and CFRTP-200 showed the partial break mode, while the others showed completely break mode. It can further confirm the reason why the impact strength of CFRTP-120 and CFRTP-200 show higher values than those of other specimens.

Figure 5: Impact strength of pure PA6 and CFRTP at different molding temperatures

4.2 DYNAMIC SCANNING ANALYSIS AND MODELING

DSC samples were heated from room temperature to 250°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min, 15°C/min, 20°C/min, 30°C/min and 50°C/min. In Figure 6, the first peak corresponds to melting of ϵ -caprolactam at around 70°C, and the second peak shows polymerization and crystallization peak during heating process. In this process, polymerization and crystallization occurs simultaneous, and both are exothermic processes. The third peak means melting of PA6, which is related to the crystallization during the heating process.

According to the second and third peak, we can calculate heat of fusion of crystallization and polymerization respectively. It can be seen that crystallinity simultaneous with polymerization was decreased by increasing the heating rate. The reason may be that synthesized polymer did not get enough time to crystallize and it reached to its melting point before finishing the crystallization process.

Figure 6: DSC thermograms of caprolactam at five different heating rates

Figure 7 represents the results from the separation of polymerization and crystallization using Gaussian distribution and Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, and the fitting data matches very well with the experimental facts at different heating rates.

Figure 7: Separation of polymerization and crystallization curve at different heating rates. (a) 10 °C/min, (b) 15 °C/min, (c) 20 °C/min, (d) 30 °C/min, (e) 50 °C/min

As mentioned above, the first order autocatalytic reaction model was used to analyze polymerization kinetics, and three parameters (A_0 , E , B_0) were calculated to analyze the relationship among polymerization rate ($d\alpha/dt$), time (t), and the degree of conversion (α) at different heating rates.

Figure 8 shows that the modeling results follows the experimental data, namely the first order autocatalytic reaction model is suitable for describing a non-isothermal polymerization.

Figure 8: Comparison of modeling results with experimental data using exponential fitting parameters

4.3 ISOTHERMAL SCANNING ANALYSIS

Figure 9 shows DSC thermograms of isothermal scanning process. At lower temperature, crystallization and polymerization occurs at the same time, because at lower reaction temperature monomer could be trapped inside of the crystals before being able to polymerize. However, at high temperature, the growth of the chains is more significant than the formation of crystals (Figure 9). It means that the molding temperature adversely affect both polymerization rate and crystallization rate; therefore, there is an optimum molding temperature for good properties of polymers.

Figure 9: DSC thermograms of isothermal scanning process

Moreover, we also separated the polymerization and crystallization peak and obtain the data for the relationship between polymerization time and the degree of the polymerization, which can be used to calculate viscosity over time.

Dave et al. [12] reported that below 50% conversion for polymerization, the complex relative viscosity ($|\eta^*| / |\eta_0^*|$) values were linear in relation to conversion for polymerization, and the viscosity of ϵ -caprolactam monomer can be described by the following (Eq. 5) & Eq. 6). The change in viscosity of the monomer during polymerization is assumed to be exponentially dependent on the polymer conversion X , which is attributed to the formation and the growth of the polymer chains.

$$|\eta^*| = |\eta_0^*| \exp(kX) \quad (X < 0.5) \quad (5)$$

Where $|\eta^*|$ is the complex viscosity of PA6 anionically polymerizing in its monomer, $|\eta_0^*|$ is the complex viscosity of caprolactam monomer, k is a constant, and X is fractional conversion. The complex viscosity of the monomer, $|\eta_0^*|$, follows an Arrhenius temperature dependence

$$|\eta_0^*|(T) = 2.7 \times 10^{-7} \exp(3525/T) \text{ (Pa.s)} \quad (6)$$

Figure 9 shows time dependent viscosity of polymerizing ϵ -caprolactam at specified temperatures. At early stage, viscosity varies almost linearly with the time. Moreover, the viscosity at 120°C increases slowly which means polymerization rate is slower than that of other cases.

Figure 9: Viscosity-time profile of ϵ -caprolactam during the first 20 seconds at different temperatures

Since viscosity of polymerizing ϵ -caprolactam varies with filling time, from these data we can obtain the relationship between filling time and the parameter which related to viscosity or the distance of flow front (Figure 10 (a)). A time when the distance of flow front has no change can be defined as the critical processing time (Figure 10 (b)), and the molding process must be finished within the critical processing time (20 seconds), regardless of the shape and size of the parts.

Figure 10: Viscosity-time profile of ϵ -caprolactam during the first 20 seconds at different temperatures

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, carbon fabric reinforced PA6 composites were manufactured by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) method. DSC analysis was conducted to evaluate polymerization kinetics of ϵ -caprolactam was for optimize molding process.

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites were prepared at five different temperatures and performed several mechanical tests. The content of unreacted monomer and water absorption of CFRTP composites are the least when the samples were molded at 140°C, and the samples which were molded at 140°C shows best bending strength and modulus. However, the impact strength of 120°C and 200°C are higher than that of others, due to high content of unreacted monomer and poor impregnation.

DSC analysis was performed to evaluated polymerization and crystallization of polymerizing ϵ -caprolactam, polymerization and crystallization occurs simultaneously, and crystallinity during polymerization process decreases by increasing the heating rate due to deficient crystallization time. In order to investigate polymerization kinetics, polymerization peak can be separated from the exothermic peak using Gaussian distribution, and we use the first order autocatalytic reaction model for modeling the polymerization kinetics. It shows a very good fit which means that the model is suitable for describing the polymerization kinetics of ϵ -caprolactam.

From the experimental and numerical analysis, it can be conclude that the optimum temperature for polymerization is 140~160°C, and the molding process must be finished within 20 seconds regardless of the shapes and sizes of the samples.

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